

Professional Competency among Teacher Educators in Self-Financing Colleges

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ABSTRACT

The Commitment of the teacher can be identified as a passion, as an investment of time, as a focus on the individual needs of the student, as a responsibility to impart knowledge, attitudes, values and belief, as maintaining professional knowledge and as an engagement with the college community. Professional Commitment on the part of teacher-educators essentially consists not only in doing their best for introducing teacher-trainees to the competencies that they would need as teachers in college, but also practically inspiring them to inculcate values of the teaching profession. The focus of the present investigation is to study the Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators serving in B.Ed. College of Education. An attempt is made to study the influence of gender, location of the Institution, Major subject and Marital status on the Professional Commitment of Teacher Educators. The study was a descriptive study.

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INTRODUCTION

Competence is skill based; standard attained and describes what people can do and what can be measured. Competences refer to the range of skills which are satisfactorily performed. Competencies can be developed through a process of observation and interviewing outstanding performers in a wide variety of jobs and roles to determine what sets these outstanding employees apart from everyone else. These characteristics can be defined in terms of behaviors – those thoughts and actions that characterize outstanding performers.

Competencies are classified as basic competencies and professional competencies. Further, professional competencies are classified into broad categories such as generic competencies, managerial competencies, and functional or technical competencies. The competencies profile has been studied during the last decades, using diverse approaches, for distinct purposes. In human resource management research, competencies are studied from the point of view of job competencies in which they are considered as technical skills to perform job activities. The term 'Soft Competencies' was defined as personal behavior or attitude. Diverse authors defined that soft competencies are complementary to technical competencies, and that they are of great importance to human resource management.

The paper deals with the review of literature, data collection, analysis and the result which is discussed in details.

Review of Literature

Srinivasan, R. (2019). Reformed the teacher education system has been a key government policy towards improving college education in India.

Joshi, M., & Bisht, D. (2019). The findings of the study revealed that teachers possessed average overall emotional intelligence. It was also found that the level of emotional intelligence and its various factors were found to be

significantly higher for the faculty members of higher education who were provided with the provision of development programmes for the faculty by the organizations as compared to the faculty members with no such provisions. Interpersonal, management and intrapersonal management combined together were the major contributing factors to the emotional intelligence level of teachers.

Sudha, S. (2019). Experiencing quick changes due to outburst of new technologies. These transformations are visible throughout biosphere together with rising countries like India, China, and Indonesia etc. These changes need to be embraced by the developing countries in sequence to get better value in education and as well as to strengthen the classroom teaching and learning process Singh, C. B. P. (2019). conducted on a sample of students (n=277) enrolled in an elite professional institute to identify variation in learning styles. Classroom ecology and teaching styles were regressed on the learning styles. Students had more choice of strategic learning style followed by deep learning style. Students opted for deep learning style when teachers adopted student-centric approach to teaching.

Chaubey, A., Bhattacharya, B., & Mandal, S. K. D. (2018). This study also explains the research done on engineering

education in India in the past and recognizes the major factors influencing the same.

Variables of the Study (6)

In research, this term refers to the measurable characteristics, qualities, traits or attributes of a particular individual, object or situation being studied. Nurses use the term variable whether they are conducting, reading or using results of qualitative or quantitative research. Researchers often refer to variable by the terms dependent or independent. Dependent variable represent outcomes of interest and they are affect by independent (i.e predictor) variables. In this study, the investigator follows independent variable and dependent variables.

An independent variable is a variable that is expected to influence the dependent variables. Its value may be changed or altered, which is independent of any other variables. Also the following demographic variables were used as independent variables.

- Gender (Male/Female).
- Medium of Study (Tamil/English).
- Type of College (Government/Private).
- Family Income (Self Employed/Salaried).
- Locality (Urban/Rural).

Sampling Techniques

The sample which was collected from various colleges located in and around Coimbatore is shown as below.

TABLE 1 LIST OF SCHOOLS USED FOR DATA COLLECTION

S. No	Name of the colleges	Number of students
1	Kasturi College of Education , Coimbatore	34
2	PPG College of Education, Coimbatore	39
3	Dr. SNS College of Education, Coimbatore	35
4	Dr. N.G.P. College of Education, Coimbatore	38
5	G .R. Govindarajulu College of Education, Coimbatore	23
6	Hindusthan College of Education, Coimbatore	31
	Total	200

TABLE 2 DISTRIBUTIONS OF SAMPLES BASED ON VARIABLES

S. No	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1	Gender	Male	61	31	200
		Female	139	70	
2	Medium of Study	Tamil	96	48	200
		English	104	52	
3	Type of College	Government	34	17	200
		Private	166	83	
4	Family income	Self Employed	91	46	200
		Salaried	109	55	
5	School Locality	Rural	81	41	200
		Urban	119	60	

Research Tool

Tool become another major consideration in an education research. The instrument employed for the collection of data required for the study of any problem is called tool. "Tool employ distinction way of describing and qualifying the data" the important tools of educational research include interview schedule, questionnaire, observation, rating scale, achievement test, proficiency test, psychological tests and sociogram.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant mean score difference between gender and the professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges.
2. There is no significant mean score difference between medium of study and the professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges.
3. There is no significant mean score difference between type of college and the professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges.
4. There is no significant mean score difference between family income and the professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges.
5. There is no significant mean score difference between locality and the professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges.

Analysis and interpretation

TABLE 3 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges based on their Gender.

S. No	Gender	N	Mean	Variance	df	t-Value	Result
1	Male	61	1.4754	0.2536	198	0.7378	Accept
2	Female	139	1.5324	0.2508			

CHART 1 LEVEL OF STUDY ON PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS IN SELF FINANCING COLLEGES BASED ON THEIR GENDER

TABLE 4 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges based on their Medium of study.

S. No	Medium of Study	N	Mean	Variance	df	t-Value	Result
1	Tamil	96	1.4271	0.2473	198	1.7145	Accept
2	English	104	1.5481	0.2501			

CHART 2 LEVEL OF STUDY ON PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS IN SELF FINANCING COLLEGES BASED ON THEIR MEDIUM OF STUDY

TABLE 5 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges based on their Type of College.

S. No	Type of College	N	Mean	Variance	df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Government	34	1.2647	0.2005	198	3.0134	0.0040	Reject
2	Private	166	1.5241	0.2509				

CHART 3 LEVEL OF STUDY ON PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS IN SELF FINANCING COLLEGES BASED ON THEIR TYPE OF COLLEGE

TABLE 6 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges based on their Family Income

S. No	Family Income	N	Mean	Variance	df	t-Value	Result
1	Self Employed	91	1.3956	0.2418	198	1.2857	Accept
2	Salaried	109	1.4862	0.2521			

CHART 4 LEVEL OF STUDY ON PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS IN SELF FINANCING COLLEGES BASED ON THEIR FAMILY INCOME

TABLE 7 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges based on their Locality.

S. No	Locality	N	Mean	Variance	df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Rural	81	1.2593	0.1944	198	3.2700	0.0013	Reject
2	Urban	119	1.4790	0.2517				

CHART 5 LEVEL OF STUDY ON PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS IN SELF FINANCING COLLEGES BASED ON THEIR LOCALITY

Finding of the analysis

- A study on high school teachers’ educator level of professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges was studied and the findings reveal that there is **a significant difference in professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges** with respect to **Gender, Medium of Study and Family Income**.
- A study on high school teachers’ level of professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges was studied and the findings reveal that there is **no significant difference in professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges** with respect to **Type of College and Locality**

Conclusion

The conclusion is high school teachers’ level of study on professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges was studied and the findings reveal that there is a significant in professional competency among teacher educators in self-financing colleges with respect to

Type of College and Locality and not with Gender, Medium of study and Family Income.

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**PERSONAL DATA SHEET APPENDICES
PROFORMA FOR BASIC DATA**

1. Name of the Teacher : _____
2. Name of the College : _____
3. Gender : Male Female
4. Medium of Study : Tamil English
5. Type of College : Government Private
6. Family Income : Self Employed Salaried
7. Locality : Rural Urban

INSTRUCTIONS

- There are some statement below. Each statement is followed by multiple choice. i.e Yes/No.
- Read each Statement carefully.
- After reading each statement mark your response in the appropriate column pitting at tick mark.

S. NO	QUESTIONARIE	YES	NO
1	I like learning Professional Competency.		
2	I will persist when facing difficulties in Professional Competency.		
3	I like listening to Professional Competency related speech.		
4	I like reading Professional Competency articles.		
5	I feel more confident in Professional Competency learning compared with my classmates		
6	I work on my Professional Competency assignments according to a planned schedule.		
7	I study Professional Competency diligently for potential development in the future.		
8	In order to know the recent development in my major, I study Professional Competency diligently		
9	Professional Competency is a very important tool for life so I study it diligently		
10	In order to get an ideal life in the future I study Professional Competency diligently		
11	Professional Competency learning takes great advantage on the future life		
12	I treat Moral values examination as an evaluation of what I have learned about Professional Competency.		
13	I like Professional Competency stories.		
14	I am excited when I have accomplished a difficult task in Professional Competency learning.		
15	I can finish my Professional Competency actively		
16	I study Professional Competency hard for the praise of the teacher.		
17	My teacher helps me to improve my Professional Competency.		
18	My Family always give lot of new words to understand Professional Competency.		
19	My teachers encourage me to participate in Professional Competency competitions		
20	I like to follow my teachers who have some sense of moral qualities		

